

D7.12: 2nd Business Model Workshop

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Executive summary

It was decided to embed the first round of workshops into the General Assembly Meeting in Koper, Slovenia on the 18th and 19th November 2019. The second round of workshops was held on 11th of May 2021 embedded in the General Assembly Meeting 10th-12th May 2021.

The workshops were designed to be even more focused and to target the key exploitable results from the project with the highest potential for further exploitation. The assessment of the partners based on the project results was that the highest potential for further exploitation is found in:

- 1) The rapeseed value stream delivering protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed application
- 2) The tomato value stream extracting a high-value ingredient (lycopene)
- 3) The citrus value stream extracting a high-value ingredient (hesperidin)

Since the 2nd workshop format was online via Teams and therefore constrained to a shorter format, it was decided to strengthen the preparation and quality of the discussions with a preparatory survey in two different formats, targeting key factors for project design (rapeseed) and business model design (tomato and citrus).

The main conclusions from the discussions will feed into a final exit-strategy of the partners in the Pro-Enrich project.

1. OBJECTIVES OF THE BUSINESS MODEL WORKSHOPS

The Pro-Enrich project will demonstrate a new business model for the financial impact and economic potential of high-value components from agricultural side streams, demonstrating how these products can be technically and commercially feasible with both small and large-scale bioprocessing units.

In order to properly prepare sustainable business models that will support the exploitation and post-project sustainability of the Pro-Enrich results and identify exploitable assets, the consortium firstly needs to capture the size of the market and major trends where new products/services are to be implemented. During the course of the project, WP7 has therefore delivered 2 business modelling workshops (M18 and M36), based on the Business Model Canvas methodology. FBCD was responsible for planning and execution of the workshops, where industrial actors in relevant application areas were invited to participate in order to capture market needs and create networks including potential end-users of the products developed in Pro-Enrich.

2. SCOPE OF THE BUSINESS MODEL WORKSHOPS

It was decided to embed the first round of workshops into the General Assembly Meeting in Koper, Slovenia on the 18th and 19th November 2019. The first business model workshop was therefore an internal workshop just for project partners.

The objective of the workshop was three-fold:

- 1) To focus the attention of the project participants – and in turn the project - on the key exploitable results of the project and the market requirements for the target compounds and processes.
- 2) To allow interaction between WPs, sharing of ideas, engaging in discussions and thereby focusing on the impact of the project results
- 3) To contribute to the overall direction and work plan of the project at the midterm stage and deliver a basis for project adjustments and (re-)focus.

The 2nd round of business model workshops was held online and embedded in the General Assembly Meeting taking place during May 10th-12th 2021. The workshops were designed to be even more focused and to target the key exploitable results from the project with the highest potential for further exploitation. The assessment of the partners based on the project results was that the highest potential for further exploitation is found in:

- 1) The rapeseed value stream delivering protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed application
- 2) The tomato value stream extracting a high-value ingredient (lycopene)
- 3) The citrus value stream extracting a high-value ingredient (hesperidin)

Since the development of these three value streams have different maturity and TRL levels and therefore different exploitation strategies, the partners decided to have two different workshops with slightly different methodologies. As regards the rapeseed value stream, the results of the project are to be exploited in further research upscaling and demonstration of the most promising technologies. On the other hand, the technology level and maturity of the citrus

and tomato value streams are closer to market application. In consequence, the partners decided on a project development workshop regarding the rapeseed value stream using a project design canvas method, while the workshop for the citrus/tomato value stream remains a classic business model workshop using the business model canvas method.

The objective of the 2nd round of workshops is therefore to start the development of and provide input to the Pro-Enrich exit and exploitation strategy.

In the following sections, we will describe the workshops in a little more detail.

2.1. Preparatory Survey

Since the 2nd workshop format was online via Teams and therefore constrained to a shorter format, it was decided to strengthen the preparation and quality of the discussions with a preparatory survey in two different formats, targeting key factors for:

- 1) project design (rapeseed)
- 2) business model design (tomato and citrus).

The preparatory survey allowed the exploitation manager and project coordinator a chance to focus attention on the most interesting/challenging issues for each value stream, to ask partners clarifying questions before the workshop and to prepare online canvasses with pre-filled key information using the Canvanizer[®]-toolbox.

Survey questions – Project design	Survey questions – Business model design
I. Why create a new project?	I. What problems do you solve for your customers?
II. What is the major change to the current state of the art introduced by the project?	Why is your solution/product important for them?
III. What tangible results do we want to deliver to the customers at the end of the project?	II. Who are your ideal customers and what are the key factors that drive their buying decisions?
IV. Who are the customers of the end product(s) of the project?	III. What would motivate your prospective customers to search for new solutions/suppliers (e.g. trends and trigger events)?
V. What are the key success parameters that would make the customer happy with the end result?	IV. What are the most important features and capabilities of your solution?
VI. What is needed to deliver the results envisioned?	V. What are the alternative options of your prospective customers?
VII. What skills are needed? What types of partners?	VI. What is your unique value proposition and competitive advantage?
VIII. What are the key costs in the foreseen project?	VII. How do you intend to reach your prospective customers and convert them into customers? (through which channels and with which methods?)
IX. Suggested funding sources?	VIII. What are your key sources of revenue (product sales, licensing, service fees) ?

2.2. Workshop format & canvas

Project design workshop				
Rapeseed value stream delivering protein concentrates/isolates for food/feed application				
Workshop themes / canvas				
Participants	Goals	Users	Activities	Deliverables
		User Benefits		
Risks		Milestones	Constraints	Scope
Brainstorming Space				

Business model workshop				
Tomato value stream extracting a high-value ingredient (lycopene)				
Citrus value stream extracting a high-value ingredient (hesperidin)				
Workshop themes / canvas				
Key Partners	Key Activities	Value Propositions	Customer Relationships	Customer Segments
	Key Resources		Channels	
Cost Structure			Revenue Streams	
Brainstorming Space				

3. EMBEDDED ONLINE WORKSHOPS

The business model workshops were executed as part of the General Assembly on the 10th-12th May 2021. Both were executed on the 11th of May 2021 as described in the programme below.

3.1. Programme for workshops - Tuesday May 11th

- 9:00-9:10** Welcome (DTI)
- 9:05 -11:30** Project Design Workshop – rapeseed proteins (FBCD/DTI)
Participants: Emmelev, GEA, T&L, Chimar, Mars, BU, Tz, Jaencoop, Leitat, Innorenew
- 11:30-12:00** Lunch
- 12:00-14:00** Business Model Workshop – lycopene and hesperidin (FBCD/DTI)
Participants: Natac, Anecoop, Chimar, GEA, Leitat, Innorenew, BU

3.2. Selection of participants in the workshops

It was decided to focus on the partners with direct involvement and business potential in the exploitation process of the specific value stream. Therefore, the participants in the discussion were selected according to their placement in the table below. Both sessions were however open to all partners, who wished to participate.

Table 3.2. Involvement in the value stream

Value stream	IPR ownership	Future processor	Primary producer	End users
Rapeseed protein	DTI (BU)	Emmelev Tailorzyme	Emmelev	Tate&Lyle, Chimar, Mars
Tomato lycopene	Natac	Natac	Anecoop	(Natac)
Citrus hesperidin	Natac	Natac GEA	Anecoop	(Chimar) (Natac)

4. DOCUMENTATION

Screenshots from the recorded workshops are shown below.

4.1. Project Design Workshop

4.2. Business Model Workshop

Business Model Workshop – afternoon - lycopene and hesperidine.mp4

Business Model Workshop – afternoon - lycopene and hesperidine.mp4

